

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF GFRP POLES

C.A. Cimini Jr.¹, H.R. Meneses², A.E.C. Sobreira¹, and E.B. Las Casas²

¹ *Department of Mechanical Engineering, Federal University of Minas Gerais, Av. Antônio Carlos 6627, Pampulha, Belo Horizonte, MG, Brazil, 31270-901*

² *Department of Structural Engineering, Federal University of Minas Gerais, Av. do Contorno 842, 2º. Andar, Centro, Belo Horizonte, MG, Brazil, 30110-060*

SUMMARY: This paper presents the results of a test program conducted on prototypes of an alternative glass fiber-reinforced plastic (GFRP) semi-monocoque lightweight pole in order to validate a computer code developed to design this kind of structure. Four-point bending test was chosen for simplicity, since poles are mainly subjected to bending loads combined to compressive loads. Prototypes were manufactured through a combination of filament winding and pultrusion processes. Instrumentation consisted of strain-gages attached to the top and bottom of the specimens, internally on the stringers and externally on the skin. A displacement transducer was positioned at midspan to measure the maximum displacement. Load was measured by a 10-ton load cell. Test results demonstrated a fairly good agreement with the predicted design, not only for stiffness but also for strength. However, design parameters conducted to a more conservative structure, which is desirable.

KEYWORDS: composite poles, experimental analysis, semimonocoque structures.

INTRODUCTION

The growing of data communication and energy transmission industries generated the necessity of investments on infrastructure to support the market expansions, which included the search for new technologies in the area of civil materials and construction techniques.

Existing structures are mainly 30 to 100 m metal truss towers, rarely exceeding 30 m in urban high density areas. Therefore, poles are the best choice due to the lack of space in cities and the concern of the organized civil society related to visual pollution.

Materials used in pole construction are currently wood, reinforced concrete or steel. However, these materials have particular high costs of design, manufacture, installation and maintenance. Wood is subject to deterioration due to environment, fungi and woodpeckers, resulting in short life expectancy and low load bearing capacity, not to mention environmental concerns. Reinforced concrete has high specific weight, which drastically increases transportation and erection costs. Also, steel reinforcement on concrete structures is subjected to corrosion and other chemical influences arising from environmental exposure. Steel also has the problems due to high specific weight with additional costs as a consequence of corrosion and fatigue preventive maintenance.

The deficiencies mentioned for the currently used materials for pole manufacture can be overcome by using new materials allied to new structural concepts. The use of composite materials together with the semi-monocoque design concept, largely used in aerospace industries, can be one alternative for pole design. Composites are natural candidates since they present high specific strength and stiffness, which can result in noticeable weight gain and desirable resistance to corrosion and fatigue. Fiber glass composites can add to poor electrical conducting desirable for electricity conductors supporting poles.

Polysois et al. [1] presented one concept glass fiber reinforced plastic hollow poles. They conducted an experimental test program with satisfactory results. This work presents a different pole concept, conceived on an alternative design approach modeled by Birchal et al. [2]. This pole is designed as a telescope mast or as a mast with constant cross-section, made of two concentric cylindrical modules reinforced by longitudinal bars equally spaced, as semimonocoque structures used aircraft fuselage (Figure 1). The fibers at the cylindrical shells are oriented in the hoop direction, while the longitudinal bars have fibers oriented in the axial direction. This philosophy brings the best that composites can offer, which are the mechanical properties on the fiber direction. Fiberglass on polyester resin was the chosen composite material in order to be cost competitive with the usual pole materials (steel or reinforced concrete) [2].

The objective of this work is to conduct a test program to verify the model proposed by Birchal et al. [2] for designing the referred pole.

Figure 1 – Semi-monocoque composite pole configuration

METHODOLOGY

The test program was based in four-point bending test. This choice was made considering that the poles are subjected mainly to bending loading. Axial loading, although important in some cases (electrical transmission lines, for example), was not considered in order to simplify test methodology. Four-point bending tests were chosen for same simplicity reasons, since the bending moment between the two applied loads is constant (Figure 2), facilitating specimen instrumentation.

Pole specimen characteristics

The pole adopted for the test program was designed [2] as a cantilever beam, clamped on its lower portion, subjected to its weight and to a concentrated shear load applied at a determined height, generating a bending moment. The model considered the longitudinal stringers responsible for the normal stresses due to bending and the concentric cylinders (skins) responsible for the shear stresses. As mentioned, fibers were oriented in the longitudinal direction on the stringers and in the hoop direction on the skins, resulting in an orthotropic-type structure. The material selected was E fiberglass on polyester resin. Pole specimen parameters are listed on Table 1. Figure 2 shows the geometry of the pole specimen.

Table 1 – Pole specimen parameters [2]

Características	Valores
Material	E-glass / polyester
Specific weight [kN/m ³]	17.66
Longitudinal Young's Modulus [GPa]	38.60
Transverse Young's Modulus [GPa]	8.26
Shear Modulus [GPa]	4.14
Poisson's Ratio	0.26
Longitudinal Tensile Strength [MPa]	1,060
Longitudinal Compressive Strength [MPa]	610
Transverse Tensile Strength [MPa]	31
Transverse Compressive Strength [MPa]	117
Shear Strength [MPa]	71.90
Pole height [m]	6.00
Thickness for the external skin [m]	0.002
Thickness for the internal skin [m]	0.002
Inner diameter of the external skin (m)	0.4508
Outer diameter of the external skin (m)	0.4548
Inner diameter of the internal skin (m)	0.396
Outer diameter of the internal skin (m)	0.400
Number of stringers	8
Longitudinal fiber orientation at the skins inner/outer	0°/0°
Longitudinal fiber orientation at the stringers	90°
Pole weight [kN]	1.2
Applied shear force [kN]	36.40
Applied shear force height [m]	6.00
Ratio Applied shear force / Pole weight	45.73
Ultimate compressive force [kN]	266
Displacement at the top [m]	0.44
Safety factor for the skins	5.83%
Safety factor for the stringers	126.5%
Possible failure mode	Skin shear

Figure 2 – Pole specimen geometry

Pole specimen manufacturing

Phase 1 – The filament winding process was used for manufacturing the inner skin, using a “Drosthholm” system machine of continuous filament, with capacity above 2,000 kg/h for GFRP (Figure 3).

Figure 3 – Inner skin

Phase 2 – The stringers were manufactured using the pultrusion process. Stringer cross section was defined as a 1 in by 1 in square (25.4 mm by 25.4 mm) in order to fit the internal space between the inner and outer skins (Figure 4).

Figure 4 – Stringers

Phase 3 – The stringers were positioned and attached to the outer surface of the inner skin using the structural adhesive Araldyte® HY951 (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – Stringers attached to outer surface of the inner skin

Phase 4 – Spaces between stringers were filled using polystyrene foam so that the outer skin could be manufactured again using the filament winding process (Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 6 – Inner skin with stringers and polystyrene foam filling

Figure 7 – Pole specimen final configuration

Pole specimen instrumentation

Four-bending tests induced maximum constant bending moment between the applied loads. Therefore this region was defined as the area for positioning the instruments, which consisted of strain (strain gages) and displacement (displacement transducer) measurement devices. Three strain gages were positioned on the specimen, two of them internally on the stringer lateral surfaces and the other externally on the skin, for both top and bottom regions of the pole specimen (Figure 8a). Top and bottom stringers were selected for strain measurements considering that these positions provide the maximum axial strain due to the pole specimen bending. Strain gages were numbered as: (1) and (2) top string lateral face, (3) top skin, (4) and (5) bottom stringer lateral face and (6) bottom skin. The displacement transducer was positioned on mid-span in order to measure the maximum displacement of the pole specimen (Figure 8b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 8 – Pole specimen instrumentation: (a) strain-gage; (b) displacement transducer

Test rig

Test program was conducted on the Experimental Analysis of Structures Lab (LAEES) of the Department of Structural Engineering (DEES) of the Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG). Pole specimens were positioned in two supports with the load applied through a hydraulic actuator with a load cell (Figure 9) attached to its end. The load was split into two points of application using a structural rig as shown in Figure 10. Test span geometry is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 9 – Load cell

Figure 10 – Test fixture

Figure 11 – Test span geometry (mm)

RESULTS

Two pole specimens were tested. Top and bottom stress-strain plots for all strain gages are respectively shown in Figures 12 and 13 for specimen 1 and in Figures 14 and 15 for specimen 2. In all figures the expected design curve is also plotted for comparison. Results fairly agreed with the design prediction.

Figure 12 – Stress-strain plots for top strain gages of specimen 1

Figure 13 – Stress-strain plots for bottom strain gages of specimen 1

Figure 14 – Stress-strain plots for top strain gages of specimen 2

Figure 15 – Stress-strain plots for bottom strain gages of specimen 2

Load vs. midspan displacement plots are shown on Figures 16 and 17, respectively for specimens 1 and 2. Displacement transducer measurement range was limited to 0.025 m.

Figure 16 – Load-displacement plot for specimen 1

Figure 17 – Load-displacement plot for specimen 2

Results for pole stiffness and strength are summarized on Table 2.

Table 2 – Pole stiffness and strength

	Stiffness ($\times 10^6$ N/m)	Shear load (kN)
Design	1.6	38.52 (*)
Specimen 1	2.0	35.70
Specimen 2	2.0	34.15

(*) Shear design load (36.40 kN) raised by the safety factor for the skins (5.83%)

CONCLUSION

A four-point bending test program was conducted to validate the alternative pole design proposed. Two pole specimens were manufactured using filament winding and pultrusion. Specimens were instrumented at the top and at the bottom with strain gages, located on the stringer and on the skin, in order to measure maximum tensile and compressive strains. A displacement transducer was positioned at midspan in order to measure the maximum displacement of the specimens.

Test results demonstrated a fairly good agreement with the predicted design, not only for stiffness but also for strength. However, design parameters conducted to a more conservative structure, which is desirable.

REFERENCES

1. Polysois, D., Ibrahim, S., Burachynsky, V. and Hassan, S.K., Glass fibre-reinforced plastic poles for transmission and distribution lines: An experimental investigation, Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Composite Materials, ICCM-12, Paris, 1999, CD-ROM.
2. Birchal, G.A, Las Casas, E.B., Cimini Jr., C.A. and Tsai, S.W., An Alternative Fiber-Reinforced Plastic Pole Design, Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Composite Materials, ICCM-12, Beijing, 2001, CD-ROM.